

DiSSCo Transition Project

**Workshop on DiSSCo Core Technical
Infrastructure**

Work Package 2 - Milestone 10

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Executive Summary

The workshop, co-organised by Work Packages 2 and 3 on 30 October 2024, aimed to discuss and prioritise next steps in the development of the core infrastructure after the development of the Minimum Viable Product (MVP) as defined in Task 3.1. As such, the workshop was open to all DiSSCo stakeholders and in particular the National Nodes. The current state of the MVP was demonstrated and options for further development were outlined, after which participants could prioritise options through two Mentimeter sessions. This was followed by an open discussion with stakeholders to collect further input for a core infrastructure roadmap outlining priorities and further development after the MVP.

Keywords

DiSSCo, data, minimum viable product, infrastructure, digitisation

List of abbreviations

API - Application Programming Interface

CA - Consortium Agreement

CMS – Collection Management System

CSO – Coordination and Support Office

D - Deliverable

DiSSCo - Distributed System of Scientific Collections

DTP - DiSSCo Transition Project

ERIC – European Research Infrastructure Consortium

EOSC - European Open Science Cloud

FAIR – Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable

GBIF – Global Biodiversity Information Facility

MAS – Machine Annotation Services

MS – Milestone

MVP – Minimum Viable Product

RI - Research Infrastructure

WP - Work Package

1. Introduction

This workshop, co-organised by Work Packages 2 and 3 of the DiSSCo Transition project (Milestone 10) provided an opportunity for the DiSSCo community to discuss and prioritise next steps in the development of the core infrastructure after the minimum viable product (MVP). As such, it was open to all DiSSCo stakeholders and in particular the National Node Representatives. The main objective was to demonstrate the current state of the MVP and outline the options for further development with backlog and use cases, after which an open discussion with stakeholders would collect input for a core infrastructure roadmap outlining priorities and further development after the MVP.

The MVP is intended for early adopters and will include around two million digital specimens, however, this may be extended shortly after the launch of the MVP to cater for the needs of identified early adopters or to test the infrastructure with a larger variety of specimen data, towards full operation in 2026.

2. Summary of the workshop

The 2.5 hour-long workshop took place on 30 October 2024 (09.30-12.00) and was well attended, with over 50 participants representing a wide range of professional profiles (with software developers and data managers being the two most represented profiles), with a good spread over Europe as well, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Locations of the workshop participants, gathered during the Mentimeter session.

Convened by Wouter Addink, the workshop was divided into several sessions, starting with the general presentation on the DiSSCo Core Infrastructure MVP by Sam Leeflang, to

provide an overview of the main components and elaborate on the functionality of the MVP and its limitations, while Wouter Addink then conveyed the current user demands and laid out the options for further development. Additionally, the Naturalis team provided a quick demo as part of the MVP presentation. The full presentation can be accessed via the [DiSSCo Knowledge Area](#), as part of the supporting documentation to the Workshop.

Figure 2: A graph from the presentation illustrating the ecosystem around the DiSSCo Core Infrastructure

Following the presentation, an interactive session with the participants took place via the Mentimeter tool, in which the audience was asked to address several aspects around stakeholder needs and first prioritisation of the Core Infrastructure. Finally, a follow-up discussion was held to complement the interactive session. The outcomes of both the interactive session and the discussion are summarised in the next section.

3. Feedback and Recommendations

The interactive session on Mentimeter set out to collect feedback from participants with regard to priorities when it comes to further development of the core infrastructure. While many different aspects were mentioned (open-ended question), several stood out as the most important: integration with GBIF, interoperability, data harmonisation, user needs and automation. In terms of ranking focal areas by priority, integration with institutional data systems was deemed the highest priority, closely followed by supporting digitisation through integration with workflows. When it comes to data-related prioritisation, data quality enhancement was firmly in the first place, with 40% of the vote. With regard to digitisation, there was once again a clear key priority selected with about 45% of the vote – integration with the institutional digitisation workflows. In terms of the different functions in support of DiSSCover users, four functions were ranked in close proximity above the rest: annotation workflows, advanced search, export functions and virtual

collections. In relation to findability and re-use, APIs and serialisations to promote integration seem to take the top spot, while label digitisation was deemed to be the most important type of data enrichment. Finally, when it comes to Machine Annotation Services (MAS), several types of support were identified by the participants as highly needed, including georeferencing, data quality improvement, data enrichment and identification. All in all, it seems that the DiSSCo partners prioritise integration with national and institutional data systems and operational workflows in the further development of the core infrastructure. Once again, the Mentimeter slides are available on the [Knowledge Area](#) along with the presentation slides.

Figure 3: Example of a question from the Mentimeter session

The last forty-five minutes of the workshop was open for discussion, in which Wouter Addink, as convener, led the discussion and posed several questions to the audience. In line with the Mentimeter responses, most participants consider it essential that DiSSCo publishes its enriched data to GBIF. Addink indicated that the DiSSCo community will not be able to provide all data until the new GBIF Unified Model is in place. For institutions providing data to DiSSCo, it is important that they are still seen as the provider of the data in GBIF, to ensure correct attribution. Besides GBIF, there might also be other infrastructures to which DiSSCo needs to publish its data. For any data that will not be pushed to data aggregators, it is important that DiSSCo provides ample search and export functionality.

A second topic central in the discussion was the annotations. The implementation of a trust model, possibly based on the iNaturalist trust model, is seen as very significant. This

might also play a role in whether an institution would want to incorporate the annotations into its Collection Management System. It became clear during the discussion that it is important for Collection Managers to be able to decide what information flows back to their CMS. In this context, the collection managers are primarily interested in the annotations generated by the MAS. This would mean that not all data that is in DiSSCo will flow back into the CMS, which is seen as acceptable by the participants.

The discussion was closed with the recognition that the community needs to monitor recent developments in the European Open Science Cloud, which may impact DiSSCo and the broader biodiversity data infrastructures.

4. Conclusion

The workshop on the DiSSCo Core Technical Infrastructure offered a timely opportunity to address the further development of the core infrastructure of the DiSSCo RI, especially given the recent progress with regard to the MVP. With over 50 participants representing most DiSSCo Nodes, the workshop served as a means to update the community on the latest developments and receive feedback going forward. Considering the Mentimeter responses and the follow-up open-ended discussion, it is clear that the Nodes prioritise interoperability of the RI with the institutional data systems and integration with digitisation workflows, and that with regard to data, the priority should be on data quality improvement. Furthermore, it will also be important to identify any other infrastructures where the data will need to be published in the future.

The recording of the workshop is available on the [DiSSCo YouTube channel](#).